

GAPS IN THE HR DIAGRAMS OF STAR CLUSTERS

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Introduction

The HR Diagram of Star Clusters is the key to understanding stellar evolution. The presence of gaps or regions of low number of stars in the diagram is interesting as it could be related to various processes of star formation or evolution. Using Gaia DR3 photometry we explore the HR diagrams of nine open clusters with reported gaps and identify them and assess their importance.

The presence of gaps or regions of small numbers of stars in the main sequence of the Hertzsprung-Russell Diagram (HRD) of star clusters has been reported in literature. This is interesting and significant as it could be related to star formation and/or rapid evolution or instabilities. In this paper, using Gaia DR3 photometry and confirmed membership data, we explore the HRD of nine open clusters with reported gaps, identify them and assess their importance and spectral types

Reported Gaps

The following gaps were reported by and are described in the table.

Structure	Position in the CM-diagram	size of the structure		
	M_V	$(B-V)_0$	ΔM_V	$\Delta(B-V)$
Mermilliod gap	0.0	-0.12	0.25	
Canterna gap	1.0	-0.05	0.20	
A-bend	1.3	-0.02	0.7	0.05
A-group	1.5	0.00	0.7	0.05
M11-gap	1.7	0.05	0.5	0.05
Böhm-Vitense gap	2.8	0.25	0.3	0.05
NGC 6134-IC 4651 gap	4.5	0.5	1.0	0.15

Fig. 1: Gaps in the main sequence

Gaps or regions of low density of stars in the HRD have been reported by various authors [4, 1, 6, 7] and could be important milestones of stellar evolution. In this paper, we present a detailed study of main sequence gaps in the HRD of a sample of nine clusters of ages ranging from $\log t = 7.09 - 9.63$ and at distances $889 - 2773$ pc using Gaia DR3 data. We use membership data and parameters from [2]. We identify the gaps, assess their statistical significance using the χ^2 test and identify their spectral types.

Cluster Sample

Our sample of nine clusters has been selected from literature of confirmed gaps with the following parameters [8].

Cluster	RA	Dec	Ang. Dia (pc)	$\log t$ age	Distance (pc)
NGC 2360	109.43	-15.64	0.03	8.65	1560.0
NGC 2477	118.05	-38.54	0.15	9.05	1442.0
NGC 2360	109.44	-15.63	0.154	9.01	1122.0
NGC 6939	307.92	60.65	0.123	9.23	1815.0
NGC 3680	171.39	-43.24	0.149	9.34	1072.0
NGC 2682	132.85	11.81	0.166	9.63	889.0
NGC 188	11.79	85.24	0.272	9.85	1698.0
NGC 2420	114.60	21.58	0.053	9.24	2587.0
NGC 6134	246.95	-49.16	0.156	8.99	1182.0

Analysis

The distribution of the nine clusters with reported gaps are shown in the figure below.

Fig. 2: The cluster sample.

We use membership data from [2] for our sample of nine clusters. As described in [3], we find the absolute magnitude and color:

$$G = G - \mu - 0.89 * A_V, (BP - RP)_0 = (BP - RP) - 0.89/1.85 * A_V$$

We plot the color magnitude diagrams (Fig. ??) and the luminosity functions (Fig. ??) to identify possible gaps in the HR diagram listed in Table ??.

We use the data from [2] to list the members of our sample. We use the color magnitude diagrams and look for possible gaps in the HR diagram. For the identified gaps, we calculate $\chi^2 = \frac{(N - N_0)^2}{N}$ as described in [4]. This is used to assess the significance of the gap. χ^2 is the probability that the gap is an accidental result.

The likelihood that the observed gap represents a chance variation can be estimated as follows. For the identified gaps, we calculate $\chi^2 = \frac{(N - N_0)^2}{N}$, where N is the expected number of stars and N_0 is the observed number of stars as described in [4]. We find the expected number as the average of the numbers before and after the gap. χ^2 is related to p that is the probability that the gap is a chance event. For a $\chi^2=4.0$, with one degree of freedom, the p value is 0.05. This means that the probability of the gap being significant is $1 - 0.05 = 0.95$, that is 95%. This implies that a smaller value implies a higher chance of the gap being significant. Table ?? lists the gaps found in our sample with their spectral types and significance. We notice the gaps we found are of similar spectral types as described in Table ??.

Characteristics of Gaps

Fig. 4: Luminosity functions of the sample of 9 clusters.

The complete paper describes the position of the gaps in some clusters if our sample with the corresponding χ^2 values.

Conclusions

In this paper, we use Gaia DR3 data and membership data of [2] to study gaps in the main sequence of the HRD of star clusters. We use the χ^2 test to find the significance of the gaps. We compare the spectral types of earlier detections and find that they agree with our present results. Gaps were reported by [5] in Gaia DR2 data for M dwarfs. In our sample, the membership data used is available only till apparent G magnitude 18 and does not include M dwarfs, we go to a spectral type of upto G, therefore we don't find that in our data. A more detailed study of HRD diagrams of star clusters is necessary to characterise these gaps and study them in more detail.

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